

Crop Insurance in India: A Study of PMFBY

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Abstract:-

More than one-third of the world's undernourished children live in India, which ranks 101th out of 116 countries in the Global Hunger Index 2021. Agriculture is a risky business due to production insecurity and market risks, which affect farmers' income levels and, as a result, food security. The purpose of this review was to comprehend the various features of various crop insurance policies in India as well as to investigate the effects of the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) on Indian farmers. In terms of the number of farmers insured, the area insured, claims paid, and total farmers benefited, agricultural insurance coverage under PMFBY has remained low. The PMFBY had significantly lower beneficiary and claim premium ratios when compared to other schemes. Farmers' premiums have a significant effect on the number of farmers insured over time, according to the multiple regression analysis, but subsidies have no effect on farmers' insurance participation. The PMFBY's major flaws are claim settlement delays, system complexity, and farmer apathy. Farmers may become more aware of these programmes if they use digital media more frequently.

Keywords:- PMFBY, Agriculture, Kharif, Government, Food Security, Financing Schemes.

Introduction:-

More than one-third of the world's undernourished children live in India, which ranks 101th out of 116 countries in the Global Hunger Index 2021 study (Global Hunger Index 2021). Agriculture is a risky business due to insecurity in production and market risks, both of which have a direct impact on farmers' income levels. Rainfed agriculture's dominance raises the riskiness of agriculture, which supports 58% of the Indian population (India Brand Equity Foundation (IBEF) 2021). Food security, according to the United Nations Committee on World Food Security, means that all people have physical, social, and economic access to enough, safe, and nutritious food to meet their food preferences and dietary needs for an active and healthy life (IFPRI 2021). Climate change, global population growth, rising food prices, and other environmental stressors are all expected to have an impact in the coming decades. Crop insurance can help farmers protect themselves against income volatility. Since independence, efforts have been made at both the national and state levels to implement a crop insurance scheme for Indian farmers. In 1972, the first crop insurance pilot programme with limited coverage began. The Pilot Crop Insurance Scheme took its place in 1978. The Comprehensive Crop Insurance Scheme, the first nationwide crop insurance scheme based on the area approach, was implemented in 1985.

The scheme was replaced in 1999 by the National Agriculture Insurance Scheme, later renamed the Modified National Agriculture Insurance Scheme. Aside from these programmes, the Indian government has launched a number of crop insurance pilot projects and programmes, such as the Crop Insurance Pilot Scheme (2000), the Farm Insurance Scheme (2003), and the Weather-Based Crop Insurance Scheme (2007). Insurance policies have been altered numerous times in order to improve results in terms of claims, premium rates, and other factors. The two crop insurance schemes currently in operation are the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana and the Restricted Weather-Based Crop Insurance Scheme.

The 'Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana' was launched by the Government of India in kharif 2016, replacing previous schemes such as the National Agriculture Insurance Scheme (NAIS) and Modified National Agriculture Insurance Scheme (MNAIS). An "area approach" was used in the insurance scheme. Until kharif 2020, when it was made optional for loanee farmers, the scheme was mandatory for farmers who took a loan from any financial source and voluntary for non-loanee farmers. The scheme was implemented by a number of public and private insurance companies, but it was overseen by the Government of India's Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers' Welfare. The "Restructured Weather-Based Crop Insurance Scheme" has replaced the "Weather-Based Crop Insurance Scheme."

Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana

The Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) was revamped in 2016, with an initial allocation of Rs. 5500 crores in the 2016-2017 union budget. This scheme offers a comprehensive risk solution at India's lowest uniform premium rate. Other crop insurance schemes, such as the National Agriculture Insurance Scheme and the Modified National Agriculture Insurance Scheme, which had flaws, have been replaced by this scheme. The insurance scheme is divided into regions. All farmers are covered by the programme, including loanees, non-loanees, tenants, and sharecroppers. The scheme, which was initially mandatory for loanee farmers who had taken a loan from any financial institution and voluntary for non-loanee farmers, was made optional for loanee farmers beginning in kharif 2020. (Indian Government, 2020) The scheme is implemented by a number of public and private insurance companies under the supervision of the Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers' Welfare. This scheme's main selling point is "one premium, one season." It addresses agricultural risks from pre-sowing to post-harvest and encourages the use of modern techniques for accurate crop yield and loss measurement, such as global positioning systems (GPS), remote sensing, smartphones, and drones, to facilitate and expedite claim settlement. All kharif and rabi crops, as well as annual horticultural and commercial crops, are covered by the scheme. Farmers pay a uniform premium rate of 2.0% for kharif crops, 1.50% for rabi crops, and 5.0% for annual horticultural and commercial crops, with the remainder split evenly between the federal and state governments. After the scheme was first implemented, several changes were made to broaden its coverage in terms of both the number of farmers and the area covered. Table 2 summarises the major changes implemented by the government thus far. The new crop insurance portal, www.agriinsurance.gov.in, was launched in 2017-2018, and a second crop insurance portal, www.pmfby.gov.in, was launched in 2018-2019 for all states. This scheme has made the Aadhar card mandatory since 2017-2018. The scheme covered crop losses caused by wild animals in 2018-2019. The Indian government implemented changes recommended by various policymakers, including: voluntary

participation of all farmers; business allocation to insurance companies for three years rather than one, from 2016-2017 to 2019-2020; limited premium subsidies (i.e., 30% for unirrigated areas and 25% for irrigated areas); an increase in the premium subsidy from 50% to 90% for northeastern states; and fixed claim cut-off dates (i.e., 0.5 percent of the total premium to be spent on information and education).

Conclusion:-

Since independence, the Indian government has launched a number of crop insurance schemes to help farmers maintain their income levels. There are currently two crop insurance schemes in operation in India: the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) and the Restructured Weather-Based Crop Insurance Scheme (RWBCIS). In comparison to previous schemes, the PMFBY has modified the following features: coverage of all kharif and rabi seasons, as well as all annual commercial and horticultural crops; risks covered from pre-sowing to post-harvesting; use of modern crop loss assessment technology, such as drones and GPS; and claims paid directly into farmers' accounts. There are three indemnity levels available: 70%, 80%, and 90%. Some new features have been added to make it more successful and farmer-friendly, such as voluntary participation for all farmers, business allocation to insurance companies for three years instead of one, linking with the Aadhaar card, mandatory requirements for states to pay subsidies on time, and flexibility for states to decide on additional risk coverage. However, we discovered that PMFBY had limited success between 2016-2017 and 2017-2018.

In addition, we discovered that agriculture insurance coverage under PMFBY remains limited in terms of the number of farmers insured, the areas insured, claims paid, and farmers benefited. The number of farmers insured fell 14.87 percent from 572.50 lakh in 2016-2017 to 481.58 lakh in 2017-2018, according to the data. Insurance company claims fell by 20.70 percent from Rs. 11,412.53 crore in 2016-2017 to Rs. 9455.12 crore in 2017-2018, as did scheme coverage, which fell by about 12.88 percent in 2017-2018 compared to 2016-2017. From 289.44 lakh in 2016-2017 to 102.26 lakh in 2017-2018, the number of farmers receiving assistance fell by 64.66

percent. The beneficiary and claim premium ratios under the PMFBY were found to be significantly lower when compared to the ratios under the National Agriculture Insurance Scheme from 2016-2017 to 2018-2019. Crop insurance schemes include the Weather-Based Crop Insurance Scheme (WBCIS), the Modified National Agriculture Insurance Scheme (MNAIS), and the Restructured Weather-Based Crop Insurance Scheme (RWBCIS).

The effects of PMFBY characteristics on farmers' coverage were investigated using a multiple regression model, which revealed that the farmers' premium had a significant effect on the number of farmers insured over the time period, despite the subsidy not playing a significant role in farmers' participation in the insurance scheme.

References:-

1. Agriculture Insurance Company of India Ltd. 2021. Evolution of Crop Insurance. Available online: <https://www.aicofindia.com>
2. Agriculture Statistics at a Glance. 2017. Directorate of Economics and Statistics; New Delhi: Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers Welfare, Government of India.
3. Agriculture Statistics at a Glance. 2018. Directorate of Economics and Statistics; New Delhi: Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers Welfare, Government of India.
4. Agriculture Statistics at a Glance. 2019. Directorate of Economics and Statistics; New Delhi: Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers Welfare, Government of India.
5. Bhushan, Chandra, and Vineet Kumar. 2017. Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana: An Assessment. New Delhi: Centre for Science and Environment.
6. Dandekar, Vinayak Mahadeo. 1985. Crop insurance in India: A review, 1976–1977 to 1984–1985. *Economic and Political Weekly*. pp. A46–A59.
7. Department of Financial Services. 2021. Restructured Weather Based Crop Insurance Scheme (2021).
8. Dey, Kushankur, and Maitra Debasish. 2017. Agriculture Insurance in India: Promise, Pitfalls, and the way forward. *Economic and Political Weekly* 52: 89–96.
9. Ghosh, Ranjan Kumar. 2018. Performance Evaluation of Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY): Part I: “Governance Analysis”. Ahmedabad: Indian Institute of Management Ahmedabad (IIMA).
10. Ghosh, Sumit. 2019. An Analysis of Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana: Expectations and Reality. *International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology* 28: 788–94.
11. Government of India. 2016. Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana: Operational Guidelines; New Delhi: Department of Agriculture, Cooperation and Farmers' Welfare, Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers Welfare, Government of India.
12. Government of India. 2018. Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana: Revamped Operational Guidelines; New Delhi: Department of Agriculture, Co-Operation and Farmers' Welfare, Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers Welfare, Government of India.
13. Government of India. 2020. Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana: Revamped Operational Guidelines; New Delhi: Department of Agriculture, Cooperation and Farmers' Welfare, Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers Welfare, Government of India.
14. Gulati, Ashok, Prerna Terway, and Siraj Hussain. 2018. Crop Insurance in India: Key Issues and Way Forward.
15. Hussain, Siraj. 2020. What Can the Centre Learn from How States Are Managing Their Own Crop Insurance Schemes? July 31.
16. India Brand Equity Foundation (IBEF). 2021. Agriculture in India: Information about Indian Agriculture and Its Importance.
17. IFPRI. 2021. International Food Policy Research Institute.
18. Jain, R. C. A. 2004. Challenges in Implementing Agriculture Insurance and Re-Insurance in Developing Countries. *The Journal* 2004: 14–23.
19. Mahajan, Shrikrishna, and Amol Bobade. 2012. Growth of NAIS: A study of crop insurance in India. *Bauddhik* 3: 1–15.
20. Mishra, Pramod K. 1994. Crop insurance and crop credit: Impact of the comprehensive crop insurance scheme on co-operative credit in Gujarat. *Journal of International Development* 6: 529–67.
21. Mukherjee, Subhankar, and Parthapratim Pal. 2017. Impediments to the spread of crop insurance in India. *Economic and Political Weekly* 52.

22. Nair, Reshmy. 2010a. Weather-based Crop Insurance in India: Towards a sustainable crop Insurance Regime? *Economic and Political Weekly* 45: 73–81.
23. Nair, Reshmy. 2010b. Crop Insurance in India: Changes and Challenges. *Economic and Political Weekly* 45: 19–22.
24. Rai, Ruchbah. 2019. Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana: An assessment of India's crop insurance scheme. *ORF Issue Brief* 16: 296.
25. Raju, S. S., and Ramesh Chand. 2008. *Agricultural Insurance in India: Problems and Prospects*; NCAP Working Paper 8. National Center for Agriculture Economics and Policy Research.
26. Tiwari, Rajesh, Khem Chand, and Bimal Anjum. 2020. Crop Insurance in India: A Review of Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY). *FIIB Business Review* 9: 249–55.
27. Tripathi, S. L. 1987. Crop Insurance in India with special reference to Comprehensive Crop Insurance Scheme. In *A Note Prepared for Induction Training Programme in Crop Insurance for Newly Recruited Assistant Administrative Officers of General Insurance Corporation of India*. Pune: Vaikunth Mehata National Institute of Cooperative Management, pp. 9–28.